

The first record of a fruit fly (Diptera: Tephritidae) from Luxembourg

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The fruit flies are represented in Europe by 266 species (Merz & Korneyev, 2004: Fauna Europaea, 1.1, <http://www.faunaeur.org>), but for a few countries (Luxembourg, Monaco, San Marino and Vatican city) no collection data has been reported in the literature. 2 ♂, 3 ♀ fruit flies from seed heads of a herbarium sample of *Centaurea jacea* L. (Asteraceae) collected in Frisange (Luxembourg near border with France) coll. 26.07.2011 were reared 30.09.2011 (T. Helminger leg.) (material deposited in alcohol at the zoological section, Museum of Natural History Luxembourg). SH placed her photo of a ♂ of that species (see below) at the forum of Diptera.Info site (http://www.diptera.info/forum/viewthread.php?forum_id=5&thread_id=42352&pid=188177#post_188177). It was identified by VAK as *Urophora quadrifasciata quadrifasciata* (Meigen 1826) based on a photo. This is the first time a Tephritidae species is recorded from Luxembourg.

